

Module 4	Python for data management (PY)
Course coordinators	Jacopo Nespola (JN) and Matteo Poggi (MP)
Lecturers	JN and MP
Class duration	30 hours
Module description	Introduction to Python language for data management. The course is in three different parts: the first one is a quick overview of the language structure and philosophy, the second on practical use of Jupiter notebooks and the third on specific Python libraries for data management.
Main topics	<p>First part: introduction to Python</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - why it is so important in data science - basic features and good practices in Python - how to check which version of Python - create and env - different env manager - Python on different OS - IDEs - Datatypes - Context managers - Functions - Classes - Super quick overview on software design (SOLID principles) in Python - Unittesting with pytest <p>Second part: Jupyter notebooks (install, configure, etc...)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Git - Release code on github/gitlab - sphinx or mkdocs - how to document your code <p>Third part: data handling and visualization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - numpy - intro - broadcast - big data in numpy - dask/zarr - alternative to numpy for big data - when and why use dask and zarr - pandas - series and data frames - missing data aggregation - pandas to sql - Matplotlib - data visualization
Objectives	On successful completion of this module students should be able to write simple Python programs and know the right tool to easily develop Python workflows on data managements.
References	Lot of online references